

Outpatient Total Addressable Market (TAM) Analysis Using Claims-Based Market Data

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Abstract

Outpatient care now accounts for a large share of healthcare delivery in the United States. Health systems increasingly depend on outpatient services for preventive care, chronic disease management, and lower-cost alternatives to inpatient treatment. At the same time, healthcare organizations are under pressure to better understand where patients receive care, which markets show growth opportunity, and how outpatient utilization differs across geographic regions. Claims-based market datasets are commonly used for these analyses, but many organizations still rely on static reports or technical tools that are difficult for non-technical stakeholders to interpret.

This study developed a reproducible outpatient Total Addressable Market (TAM) framework using claims-based outpatient encounter data aggregated across multiple geographic markets. Outpatient TAM was defined as the total outpatient encounter volume within each market. Analyses examined variation in market share across health systems and differences in outpatient utilization by service line. Findings were translated into tables, figures, and dashboard-ready visualizations intended to support operational and strategic planning. Results showed major variation in outpatient market concentration across both health systems and specialties. Christus accounted for the largest overall outpatient market share

across the analyzed markets, while Ardent maintained a meaningful share of outpatient encounters across several high-volume service lines. Certain specialties, including Behavioral Health and Musculoskeletal services, showed substantial fragmentation among smaller providers. Other categories, such as Cardiovascular services, were more heavily concentrated among dominant health systems.

The project shows that claims-based outpatient TAM analysis can support healthcare organizations in identifying utilization patterns, competitive positioning, and potential areas for outpatient expansion. Converting complex claims data into accessible visual tools may improve strategic planning and help organizations better align outpatient services with population needs.

1. Introduction

Outpatient care has become a central part of healthcare delivery in the United States. More services that once required inpatient hospitalization are now managed in ambulatory settings, including chronic disease management, preventive care, diagnostic testing, and specialty consultations. National health expenditure data show that physician and outpatient services continue to represent a large share of overall healthcare spending (Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services [CMS], 2023). Healthcare organizations use claims-based analytics to understand how patients move across healthcare markets and where care is delivered. These datasets make it possible to evaluate utilization trends, compare market share across systems, and identify variation in outpatient activity between geographic areas. Most organizations already have access to this type of information. The problem is commonly interpretation.

Many existing market reports are difficult for operational leaders to use. They often depend on static spreadsheets, disconnected dashboards, or technical analytics that require significant interpretation by analysts before leadership teams can act on the results. Outpatient analyses are also frequently separated from broader market share reporting, making it harder to evaluate the full outpatient landscape within a region. Population health literature has consistently shown that healthcare utilization is influenced by both patient characteristics and healthcare system structure. Aday and Andersen (1974) described access to care as a combination of system organization, availability of services, and patterns of healthcare use. Andersen's Behavioral Model later expanded this framework by emphasizing that utilization is shaped by demographic, social, economic, and organizational factors in addition to medical need (Andersen, 1995).

Research on healthcare variation also shows that higher utilization does not automatically translate into better outcomes or improved access. Fisher et al. (2003) found that regions with higher Medicare spending often delivered substantially more services without corresponding improvements in quality or access to care. Finkelstein et al. (2016) similarly demonstrated that regional variation in healthcare utilization is influenced by both patient demand and local supply-side characteristics, including provider availability and practice patterns. Those findings matter because healthcare organizations often interpret outpatient growth opportunities strictly through market share percentages or encounter counts. That approach misses the larger picture. Geographic variation, provider concentration, referral structures, and fragmentation across smaller organizations all influence how outpatient care is distributed.

This project focused on building a practical outpatient Total Addressable Market framework using claims-based market data across multiple geographic markets. The goal was not to create a predictive model or a highly technical analytic product. The goal was to create a reproducible and interpretable framework that operational teams could actually use.

The study had four primary objectives. First, it aimed to quantify outpatient market share variation across health systems. Second, it examined differences in outpatient utilization across service lines. Third, it translated findings into structured visualizations and dashboard-ready outputs. Finally, it evaluated how claims-based outpatient analytics could support strategic planning and population-informed decision-making within a healthcare organization.

2. Methods

Study Design

This project used a descriptive cross-sectional design to evaluate outpatient market activity across multiple geographic markets within a multi-market healthcare organization. The analysis focused on outpatient encounter distribution, market share variation, and service line concentration across competing health systems. The broader purpose of the project was operational rather than clinical. The study aimed to create a reproducible outpatient Total Addressable Market framework that could support strategic planning and improve interpretation of claims-based market data for non-technical stakeholders.

Data Sources

The primary data source was a licensed healthcare claims dataset containing outpatient encounter information aggregated across multiple geographic markets. The dataset included outpatient encounter volume, service line classifications, health system attribution, and market identifiers. Supporting market definition files and service line to market mapping tables were used during aggregation and reporting. A lookup calendar data set was used to ensure relationships between data sets were properly established. Claims-based market data were selected because they provide broad visibility into outpatient utilization patterns across healthcare systems and geographic regions.

Study Population

The analytic population consisted of outpatient encounters captured within the claims dataset during the selected study period. Analyses were conducted at the market and service line level rather than the patient level. Encounters were aggregated by geographic market and outpatient specialty category to support comparison across health systems, and patient-specific data was removed to align with privacy requirements.

Variables and Measurements

Key variables included health system attribution, outpatient service line classification, geographic market identifiers, and outpatient encounter volume. Derived measures included total outpatient TAM volume, defined as the total outpatient encounter activity within each market, along with market share percentages representing the proportion of encounters attributed to each health system. Additional calculations evaluated differences in outpatient

market concentration across specialties and compared Ardent's outpatient market share against leading competitors within each service category. Potential confounding factors were considered during interpretation of results. These included provider availability, referral structures, geographic service distribution, and local market characteristics that could influence outpatient utilization patterns.

Data Preparation and Quality Assurance

Several validation steps were completed before analysis. Data quality checks included evaluating missingness across key variables, reviewing encounter distributions, confirming consistency of service line categories, and validating aggregated totals. Market names were modified in the data source to align with company standards. Duplicate records and anomalies were reviewed and removed when necessary. This included any blanks or errors as reviewed in the power query. Service line classifications were standardized using existing claims-based groupings to support consistent comparison across markets.

Outpatient TAM Framework

Outpatient Total Addressable Market was defined as the total outpatient encounter volume captured within each geographic market. Market share percentages were calculated by dividing the outpatient encounter volume attributed to each health system by the total outpatient encounter volume within the analyzed markets. The framework intentionally remained simple. The point of the analysis was to create something transparent and reproducible that could be extended to future reporting periods without requiring highly

specialized statistical modeling. All of the measures and clean up was done in the development stage to ensure that recurring updates were feasible.

Analysis Approach

The analysis was descriptive and comparative, with Market-level summaries generated to evaluate outpatient market concentration across health systems. Additional analyses examined variation in outpatient encounter distribution by service line and identified areas where outpatient activity was concentrated among a small number of dominant organizations. Results were translated into tables, figures, and dashboard-ready visualizations to improve interpretation for operational stakeholders.

Software and Visualization

Power BI was used for data modeling, visualization development, and dashboard construction. Power query and DAX calculations were completed in Power BI to obtain the insights required to build a thorough analysis of each market. Microsoft Excel was used for preliminary validation, data inspection, and limited transformations. Visualizations were designed to support interpretation of outpatient utilization patterns rather than provide highly technical statistical output. Visualizations were primarily created in Power BI and easily transferable to PowerPoint for reporting as needed.

Ethical Considerations

This project used secondary administrative claims data for operational and analytic purposes. No patient-level analyses or direct patient interactions occurred. Data access and use

followed organizational governance requirements and Institutional Review Board review was not anticipated because the analysis relied on aggregated secondary data used for operational planning rather than human subjects research.

3. Results

Overall Outpatient Market Share

Analysis of outpatient encounter distribution showed substantial concentration among a limited number of health systems, with Christus representing the largest overall outpatient market share across the analyzed markets. Ardent accounted for approximately 28% of outpatient encounters. Baylor Scott & White and Bingham Memorial represented smaller portions of total outpatient activity. The distribution was not balanced across organizations. A small number of systems controlled a large share of outpatient utilization within the analyzed regions.

Distribution of Outpatient Encounters by Service Line

Behavioral Health represented the highest-volume outpatient service line in the dataset, followed by Musculoskeletal services and General Medicine. Cardiovascular services also showed high outpatient encounter volume relative to other specialties. Lower-volume categories among the top-ranked service lines included ENT and Family History or Health Status-related encounters. These findings showed clear variation in outpatient concentration across specialties with some categories heavily concentrated among large organizations, and others remained fragmented across multiple smaller providers.

Market Share by Service Line

Service Line	Ardent (%)	Largest Competitor (%)	Other (%)
Behavioral Health	1.47	Presbyterian (6.80)	85.14
Cardiovascular	9.12	Christus (17.37)	51.43
Dermatology	4.41	Presbyterian (9.23)	70.97
Endocrinology	5.41	Christus (14.54)	54.7
Gastroenterology	7.11	Christus (17.36)	47.43
General Medicine	5.49	Presbyterian (16.84)	50.45
Musculoskeletal	3.1	Christus (9.12)	70.03
Oncology	5.37	Presbyterian (12.74)	54.42
Pulmonology	7.77	Presbyterian (10.46)	60.5
Urology	6.22	Christus (9.06)	64.12

Service-level analyses demonstrated meaningful differences in outpatient market penetration across specialties. Ardent demonstrated stronger positioning in Cardiovascular services and Pulmonology compared with several other specialties. Christus maintained dominant outpatient market share in Cardiovascular services, Gastroenterology, and Endocrinology.

Presbyterian held a substantial share of outpatient encounters in Behavioral Health, General Medicine, and Oncology. Several service lines also showed large percentages categorized within “Other” providers. Behavioral Health and Musculoskeletal services demonstrated particularly high fragmentation among smaller organizations. That level of fragmentation matters because it suggests portions of the outpatient market remain distributed across many independent or smaller healthcare entities rather than concentrated within dominant systems.

4. Discussion

This study developed a reproducible outpatient Total Addressable Market framework using claims-based outpatient market data across multiple geographic regions. The findings showed major variation in outpatient utilization across both health systems and service lines. Some specialties were heavily concentrated among dominant organizations, while others remained highly fragmented across smaller providers. That variation supports what previous healthcare utilization literature has already shown. Healthcare use is strongly shaped by organizational structure, provider supply, referral patterns, and local market characteristics. The results aligned closely with findings from Fisher et al. (2003), who reported that healthcare utilization patterns vary substantially across regions without necessarily improving quality or access. The current study similarly found that outpatient concentration differed significantly across markets and specialties. Finkelstein et al. (2016) also demonstrated that both patient demand and local healthcare supply contribute to regional utilization differences. The outpatient variation observed in this analysis likely reflects many of those same structural influences.

One of the clearest findings from this project was the level of fragmentation across certain outpatient specialties. Behavioral Health and Musculoskeletal services contained especially large shares of encounter activity distributed across smaller organizations categorized as “Other.” That fragmentation creates both operational challenges and strategic opportunities where healthcare systems attempting to expand outpatient presence in fragmented specialties may face more competition from smaller local providers, referral networks, and community-based organizations. At the same time, fragmented markets may provide opportunities for improved coordination, outpatient expansion, and service integration.

Another important aspect of the project involved usability. A major problem with many healthcare market analyses is that they are difficult for non-technical stakeholders to interpret. Analysts often understand the outputs, but operational leaders may struggle to translate those findings into planning decisions. This project intentionally prioritized clarity over technical complexity. The framework was designed to support interpretation by strategy teams, operational stakeholders, and leadership groups without requiring advanced statistical expertise.

Several limitations should be considered. The analysis relied on claims-based outpatient encounter data and did not include patient outcomes, quality measures, or clinical severity indicators. Market definitions and service line categorizations were dependent on the structure of the source dataset. Variation in coding practices or attribution methods may also have influenced encounter classification across markets. The project was descriptive rather than causal. The findings identify patterns and variation in outpatient utilization but do not establish causal relationships between healthcare market characteristics and outpatient

activity. Future work could expand the framework by incorporating payer mix, longitudinal trend analysis, demographic stratification, or financial performance measures. Additional analyses examining relationships between outpatient market concentration, healthcare access, and population health outcomes would also strengthen the framework.

The biggest strength of this project was practicality. Healthcare organizations already have enormous amounts of claims-based market data available to them. What many organizations lack is a simple and reproducible way to organize that information into something operational teams can actually use. This framework addressed that gap by converting complex outpatient market data into structured visualizations and comparative analyses that support planning and decision-making.

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